

English Translations of India Literature in Colonial India

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Abstract:

Translations are always embedded in cultural and political systems, and in history. For too long translation was seen as purely an aesthetic act, and ideological problems were disregarded. Yet the strategies employed by translators reflect the context in which texts are produced. In the nineteenth century, an English translation tradition developed, in which texts from Arabic or Indian Languages were cut, edited and published with extensive anthropological footnotes. The present work attempts to focus on strategies of colonial translators to uphold supremacy over culture and literature of the colonized.

As English becomes an increasingly global language, so more people become multilingual and translation becomes a crucial communicative activity, whereas traditional thinking about translation saw it as a poor copy of an original, today translation is viewed as an act of invention that produces a new original in another language.

Translations are always embedded in cultural and political systems, and in history. For too long translation was seen as purely an aesthetic act, and ideological problems were disregarded. Yet the strategies employed by translators reflect the context in which texts are produced. In the nineteenth century, an English translation tradition developed, in which texts from Arabic or Indian languages were cut, edited and published with extensive anthropological footnotes. In this way, the subordinate position of the individual text and the culture that had led to its production in the first place was established through specific textual practices. The Arabs, Edward Lane informed readers in notes to his popular translation of *The Thousand and One Nights*, were far more gullible than educated European readers and did not make the same clear distinction between the rational and the fictitious (Lane 1859). In similar vein, Edward Fitzgerald, author of one of the most successful translations of the nineteenth century, *The Rubaiyat of Omar Khayyam*, could accuse the Persians of artistic incompetence and suggest that their poetry became art only when translated into English (Bassnett 1991). Both these translators were spectacularly successful, but when we start to examine the premises upon which their translation practice was based, what emerges is that they clearly saw themselves as belonging to a superior cultural system. Translation was a means both of containing the artistic achievements of writers in other languages and of asserting the supremacy of the dominant, European culture.

When Sir William Jones (1746-96) translated the Sanskrit romantic play *Abhijnanashakuntalam* into English as *Sacotala*, or the *Fatal Ring: An Indian Drama* (1789), a major departure into English as *Sacotala*, of the *Fatal*

Ring: An Indian Drama (1789), a major departure he made from the Introduction 7 original was to stop the tender lovelorn heroine from breaking into sweat every now and then. Having lived in Calcutta as a judge of the Supreme Court there since 1783 he could not but have noticed that the climate was appreciably warmer, but he still felt obliged to mitigate this essential bodily function in the interests of his Western notion of the aesthetic. He would not have known, with the *Kama Sutra* yet to be 'discovered' and translated, that to sweat was traditionally known and appreciated in India also as a visible symptom of sexual interest and arousal (in contrast with England, where one sweats when one is 'hot, ill, afraid or working very hard', Collins 1987: 1477), nor could he have taken while horses sweat and men perspire, women glow. Anyhow, his act of prim and proleptically Victorian censorship neatly points up the common translatorial temptation to erase much that is culturally specific, to sanitize much that is comparatively odorous.

Sir William Jones was, of course, universally acclaimed till the other day as 'Oriental Jones' (cannon 1964), in pre-Saidian innocence and even reverence. He pioneered translation into English of Indian (specifically Sanskrit) as well as Arabic and Persian texts, and helped bring about a new awareness of oriental literature which initially caused such tremendous excitement among some of the best and most creative European minds of that age as to have precipitated nothing less than an 'Oriental Renaissance' – or so it then seemed (Schwab 1948: 4-8) what is notable here is that now, as for some decades afterwards, the traffic in translation between the East and the West remained decidedly one-sided, from the East to the West. However, through the nineteenth century and well into the twentieth, even when a regular flow of translations from English into the Indian languages had been inaugurated, nearly as many works from Sanskrit continued to be translated into the modern Indian languages as from English, and often by the same new multilingual Janus-faced Indian translators. Throughout this period, the Indian literary space was a vigorously contested terrain,

with the impulse for an eager reaction of the new western modes of literature being counterpointed by a tendency to resist such influence, often through reasserting the older indigenous forms of Indian writing. Eventually, however, the resurgence of native traditions gave way to a hegemony of Western literary culture even as the British colonial dominance grew way to a hegemony of Western literary culture even as the British colonial dominance grew more entrenched all round. A striking instance of the new literary climate was a flurry of about a dozen translations into Hindi in the 1920s and 1930s of the Rubaiyat of Omar 8 Susan Bassnett and Harish Trivedi Khayyam. These were, of course, translations of a translation, an instance indeed of orientalism translated, and perhaps even a foreshadow, so to say, of the Empire translating back. For several of these translations were strongly modified Indian adaptations, while a couple had been done straight, from Persian, which had been the elite court-language of India for several centuries before English supplanted it under the Macaulay-Bentinck diktat from 1835 onwards, and in which many cultured Indians were still well versed a century later. Thus, while multiple translations into Hindi of Edward Fitzgerald's Omar Khayyam may have underlined the condition of colonial dependence in which Indians now gained access to Persian can be seen as a resolute act of resistance to the English intervention. In any case, the most successful of all these translations (of new and inspired versions), Madhushala (i.e. The House of Wine;1935) by the most popular romantic poet in Hindi this century, Harivansha Rai Bachchan (1907-), was a wholesale appropriation of the Rubaiyat to the local cultural and even topical nationalish context (Trivedi 1995: 29-52). Thus, if the Persian poets such as Khayyam and Attar needed to be supplied with 'a little Art' by Fitzgerald before they could become acceptable in English, Fitzgerald in turn needed to be fairly comprehensively modified and even subverted before he could be metamorphosed into successful Hindi poetry. If Bachchan's Madhushala is at all translation, it is translation as rewriting, as Andre Lefevre has called it of translation as 'new writing', as Sujit Mukherjee has named it in the Indian literary context (Mukherjee 1994: 77-85). In India, with its long history of oral composition and transmission and the dominant early phase of bhakti or devotional poetry in all its modern languages in which the poet surrendered to and sought to merge his individual identity with his divine subject, the distinction between different composers of poetry within the same tradition of between an original writer and a translator was never half as wide as it has been in the West. Indeed, Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak's uncharacteristically tender plea that a translator

should adopt a procedure of 'love' and 'surrender' towards the original, as she herself claims to have done when translating from the Bengali some devotional poetry as well as the contemporary fiction writer Mahasweta Devi, may be seen as vestigial persistence of these traditional Indian practices (Spivak 1993:180-1). It is relevant in this regard that the printing of books started in India on any significant scale only towards the end of the eighteenth century. Charles Wilkins, an Introduction 9 early orientalist and translator from Sanskrit, also designed and cast the first font of Bengali characters and founded in 1778 in Calcutta a printing press which was generously patronized by the East India Company (Brockington 1989: 96), the Indian incunabulum thus may be said virtually to comprise books published before 1801. The rise of print capitalism in India was thus a modern-colonial phenomenon as was the birth of the individual copyright-holding 'author', whose 'death' and 'function' have lately been debated in the West by Roland Barthes and Michel Foucault. Such an author could no longer be simply and silently rewritten; he needed to be scrupulously, even faithfully, translated.

The word for translation in Sanskrit, which persists unchanged in most of the modern Indian languages, is *anuvad*, which etymologically and primarily means 'saying after or again, repeating by way of explanation explanatory repetition or reiteration with corroboration or illustration, explanatory reference to anything already said' (Monier-Williams 1997:38). (One of the early Sanskrit uses of the word in this sense occurs in the Brihadaranyaka Upanishad in a passage which T. S. Eliot picked up for use in the last section of the waste Land; Eliot's 'What the Thunder Said' is, in the Sanskrit source, strictly speaking what the Thunder Translated/Tepeate- for the syllable DA had already been first uttered by the god Prajapati.) The underlying metaphor in the word *anuvad* is temporal to say after, to repeat –rather than spatial as in the English/ Latin word translation – to carry across. Thus 'imitation' in the neo-classical sense was in India a form of translation as being a repetition of something already written, and formed the staple of the pre-colonial literary tradition with those two great sources –books of Indian culture, the Ramayana and the Mahabharata, being worked and reworked by countless writers in Sanskrit itself as well as in all the modern Indian languages, with various shifts of emphasis and ideology through which gaps in the original were inventively filled in, silence were rendered poignantly articulate, and even some of the great heroes turned into villains and villains into heroes.

The most outstanding examples of literature as an accumulative endeavor constantly to make it

new are the standard versions of these two great epics in nearly every one of the modern Indian languages. Each of these versions, which were done on the whole sometime between the tenth and the sixteenth centuries AD, is clearly and substantially based on the Sanskrit original it repeats or retells, but with sufficient indisputable originality based on the Sanskrit original it repeats or retells, but with sufficient indisputable originality for it to be regarded by everyone 10 Susan Bassnett and Harish Trivedi as an autonomous freestanding creative work of the first order. For example, Tulsi Das (1532-1623) is still regarded as the greatest poet ever in Hindi for having (re-)written the Ramayana. Such was his own poetic genius that he enjoys the status in Hindi, incredible as it may sound, of both Shakespeare and the Authorised Version of the Bible put together in English. Tulsidas was by birth a brahman. Even as he brought this scriptural epic to the 'vernacular' masses by releasing it from the monopolist custody of Sanskritpundits, by whom he was predictably derided and harassed, he remained, as decreed by religious tradition and caste, entirely non-violent and a vegetarian. His reformational act of the appropriation of the Ramayana could thus hardly be called an instance of Brazilian cannibalism, it marked, rather, a natural process organic, ramifying, vegetative growth and renewal, comparable perhaps with the process by which an ancient banyan tree sends down branches which then in turn take root all around it and comprise an intertwined family of trees: *quod rami non arbores*. Such symbiotic intermingling of the original with the translation, of the tradition with the individual genius, still persists and is seen as sanctioning the practice, fairly widely prevalent in contemporary India, of transcreation (Lal 1996). Indeed, this word is listed in a new supplement of 'Indian English' words in the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Contemporary English (5th edn, 1996), along with such exotically incomprehensible terms as *tota* and *trishul*- unmindful of the fact that transcreation is a term which has independently been used also on the other side of the globe, by Haroldo de Campos in Brazil (as shown in Else Vieira's chapter in this volume).

A crucial disjuncture between the older pre-colonial translational practice in India (of which different aspects are highlighted in this volume in the chapters by G. N. Devy and by Vanamla Viswanatha and Sherry Simon) and the present post-colonial phase is that now, translations from the various Indian languages into English, whether done by foreigners or by Indians themselves, have attained a hegemonic ascendancy. The widely shared postcolonial wisdom on the subject is that the Empire can translate back only into English, of into that lower or at least lower – case variety of it,

English, according to some pioneering and influential theorists of the subject (Ashcroft et al. 1989: 8) To any counter-claims that literature especially with a postcolonial thrust is being written equally or even more abundantly in languages other than English, especially in countries such as India where only a small elite (variously estimated to constitute between 2 Introduction 11 and 10 per cent of the population) knows any English, the usual skeptical Western retort, is : But show us – in English translation (Trivedi and Mukherjee (eds) 1996: 239). Yet, in inveterately multilingual countries such as India, not only is most literature being written now in the indigenous languages but the majority of translations being done are from one Indian language into the others. In 1996, when Mahasweta Devi translated, introduced and theorized in English by no less a post-colonial authority than Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak received India's highest literary award, the Jnanpeth (at a ceremony at which a special guest was Nelson Mandela) and acknowledge in her acceptance speech the role played by translation in gaining her a wider audience beyond Bengali in which she writes, she mentioned with gratitude the role played not by Spivak or any others of her translators into English but rather by Arvind Kumar, the then director of the National Book Trust of India, and earlier a Hindi publisher himself, who had for many years facilitated the translation and dissemination of her works into Hindi and other Indian languages. There are thus two Mahasweta Devis, the one addressing the political and cultural realities on her native ground in her native language as these have evolved over a long stretch of both colonial and post-colonial times (right from her first novel, which had for its heroine Rani Lakshmi Bai one of the most valiant fighters against the British during the 'Mutiny of 1857, to her more recent work describing the present – day struggles of the tribals and Marxist revolutionaries against the independent Indian nation-state), and the other the author of a few selected short stories which through English translation have been borne across and coopted within the post-colonial agenda set by the western academy. And there are many Mahasweta Devis in each of the Indian languages whose writings engage with a whole range of postcolonial issues but who are yet untranslated into English and therefore unknown to postcolonial discourse.

The question to be asked here is: can one be thought to be a postcolonial even before or without being translated into English? Does s/he even exist before so translated? It is an understandable urge for simple self-assertion which in a large measure accounts for the great translation boom currently on in India in which any number of Indians have taken it upon themselves to translate works of Indian

literature, both ancient and modern, into English to show the world (including Anglophone Indians) that such works do exist. A. K. Ramanujan, probably the most outstanding Indian translator in the half century since Independence, set an example in this regard through his own 12 Susan bassnett and Harish Trivedi informed and conscientious practice, as Vinay Dharwadker's chapter on him in this volume demonstrated.

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